

Fadama III as a Poverty Reduction Programme in Benue State: A Review

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Abstract

As the quest to see poverty reduced to the lowest minimum continues, the government at various levels in Nigeria have come to realise the need for leverage on development assisted programmes that will help meet this need. This paper examined Fadama III as a poverty reduction programmes in Benue State: a review. Findings revealed certain components of the Fadama III programme that help reduce poverty in Benue State. Specifically, results showed that capacity building, communications and information support as well as rural infrastructure are essential components that help in poverty reduction in the study area. Furthermore, findings revealed that to help develop a saving culture among Fadama User Groups (FUGs), there is need to establish a savings scheme in order to promote community level capitalization as well as to ensure sustainability of the investment activities with the matching grants and counterpart funds. Nonetheless, results also delineate some challenges of the programme and due to these findings, it was therefore recommended that administrators of the programme give proper attention to issues relating to timely disbursement of the programme grant as this is a major set back identified in the implementation of the programme in Benue State.

Keywords: Fadama III, Poverty reduction, Grant disbursement, Beneficiaries, Saving.

Introduction

In an attempt to reduce poverty in Nigeria, successive governments have initiated poverty reduction strategies at different times, most of which were replicated or applied directly at the state levels. All the programmes launched by the Federal Government were also implemented at the State levels. However, Benue State also initiated and implemented its own poverty reduction programmes. The Aper Aku administration launched the Economic Development Package (EDP) and also established the Benue State Rural Development Agency (BERDA) in 1994 to help alleviate the sufferings of Benue people. Also, the George Akume administration launched Benue Advanced Plan (BAP) and Hope Alive Foundation in 2001, and Local Empowerment and Environmental Management Project (LEEMP) in 2004, while the Gabriel

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Suswam Administration launched Our Benue Our Future in 2007 and Sev-Av Foundation in 2008. However, the incidence of poverty in Nigeria is lamentably high [1] and Benue is one of the poorest states in Nigeria. Hence if the data on the incidence of poverty in the study area is anything to go by, then the above programmes failed to meet the purpose for which they were designed.

Moreover, the status of human development in Nigeria has not shown remarkable improvement in spite of the changes in the social and economic conditions in recent years couple with the foreign assistance like *Fadama III*. Economic growth in Nigeria has not been associated with food security and poverty reduction has not abated in turn slowing down the rate of improvement in human development as evidenced by only marginal improvement in the HDI between 2012 and 2015. It is for this reason that *Fadama III* as a poverty reduction programme in Benue State: a review is examined in this study.

Third *Fadama* Programme in Nigeria of 2009

The project is a comprehensive five-year action programme spanning between 23rd March 2009 – 31st December 2013, developed by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources in close collaboration with the Federal Ministry of Environment and other Federal and State Government Ministries, Local Governments and key stakeholders (donors, private operators, NGOs) *Fadama* areas are flood plains and shallow aquifers found along Nigeria's major river systems. The first *Fadama* project (*Fadama I*) focused exclusively on irrigation farming while both *Fadama II* and *Fadama III* are more of agricultural diversification programs, providing finances for the diverse livelihood activities which the beneficiaries themselves identify and design, with appropriate facilitation support [2]. The project intervened in all 36 states plus the FCT. The beneficiaries were encouraged to organize themselves into Economic Interest Groups, named *Fadama* User Groups (FUGs) each having an average of 10 to 25 members, in addition, they will be facilitated to establish *Fadama* Community Associations which are apex organizations of 15 FUGs on average at the community level [2].

Objectives and Implementation Strategy of *Fadama III* Project

The development objective of the *Fadama III* project was to increase the income of users of rural land and water resources on a sustainable basis [1]. By increasing their incomes, the project helped reduce rural poverty, increase food security and contribute to the achievement of a key millennium development goal. Specifically, the project aims at sustainably increasing the income of *Fadama* resource users by directly delivering resources to them (i.e., the beneficiary rural communities), efficiently and effectively; and empowering them to collectively decide on how resources are allocated and managed for their livelihood activities and to participate in the design and execution of their sub-projects.

The objectives of the programme were:

- to build capacity among participants on agriculture and business;
- to facilitate the establishment of small-scale enterprises; to achieve adequate input supply to farmers and entrepreneurs; and
- to help farmers and entrepreneurs achieve adequate output and income.

The team of facilitators was deployed in each community to provide training and technical assistance support to ensure that *Fadama* resource users, including women and other vulnerable groups, have a voice in the decision-making process and benefit equally from project inputs.

These objectives were achieved through the financing and implementation of four main components designed to transfer financial and technical resources to the beneficiary groups, the FCAs in [2]:

- i. institutional and social capital development;
- ii. physical infrastructure for productive use;
- iii. income-generation and livelihood improvements; and
- iv. transfer and adoption of technological know-how; as well as
- v. implementation coordination.

The project will be coordinated by the National *Fadama* Coordination Office (NFCO) of the NFRA, the implementing agency of the FMAWR, while the day-to-day implementation will mainly take place at the state level. The project aims to cover an estimated 7,400 *Fadama* Community Associations in 36 participating states including FCT. Each new participating state will implement project activities in up to 20 Local Government Areas (PIM No.1, 2009, p. 3). At the state level the State Ministry of Agriculture has delegated the day-to-day operations to the State *Fadama* Coordination Office. Decision making is decentralized and demand-driver. The target population of the project is 2.2million rural farming households, the target group includes;

1. Small holders: Male and female (farmers, pastoralists, fisher folks, traders, processors, hunters and gatherers).
2. The disadvantaged and physically challenged group (Widows/ widowers, the handicapped, the unemployed youth, PLWHN etc).

Service providers, including government agencies, private operators and professional/semi professional associations operating in the project [1].

Components of the *Fadama III* Project

With a main paradigm shift for *Fadama III*, from change of supply driven to demand-driven approach and move from subsistence to commercial agriculture. The project as stated by (PIM No. 1, pp. '5-11') is arranged into six (6) components; (a) capacity building for Local government and communication support, (b) small-scale community owned infrastructure (c) advisory services and inputs support (d) support to agricultural development projects (ADPs), (e) asset acquisition for individual *Fadama* user groups (FUGs) economic interest groups (EIGs) and (f) project management, monitoring and evaluation and environmental management plan (EMP). These components are exposted as follows:

Capacity Building, Communications and Information Support

This component aims at supporting measures to build the capacity of *FADAMA* Community Associations (FCAs) to carry out participatory planning, to implement, operate and maintain projects, to administer funds and to negotiate conflicts. In identifying priorities of individual FCAs through participatory planning, particular attention was paid to marginalized and vulnerable groups. The output of this planning process is the local development plan (LDP), which comprises among others, a plan for training and building the capacity of FCAs [2]. This component also undertakes sensitization of stakeholders and policy makers to raise their awareness and understanding of the project objectives, approaches,

implementation arrangements and mechanism for discussing and resolving conflicts. The *Fadama III* Communication Strategy should address issues, which are separated into generic and overarching issues, with respect to: the State authorities, Local Government Areas, and those for the communities. Specifically, the component addresses each of the issues by identifying a target group of people who need to change attitudes, behavior or knowledge to help *Fadama III* become more successful; the significance of each of these issues to the successful implementation of *Fadama III* is then described; based on the particular issue and its significance to the Project, an appropriate communication intervention is recommended; the key messages which form the content of the intervention are described; and the resources (people, equipment, communication medium and timeframe) needed to implement the intervention are identified. The communication strategy therefore, consists of a set of practical responses to the communication issues and needs specific to *Fadama III*, based on the experiences of *Fadama II* [1]. It is important that the *Fadama III* has access to a number of communication service providers with sufficient capacity to support the implementation of the overall communication needs of communities, local governments and states. There should be a heavy reliance on the expertise of skilled media producers and service providers in design, printing, audio/video recording etc. in each participating State. The Capacity Building, Communication and Information Support Component will be implemented at four levels as follows: community, Local Government, State Government and Federal Government levels. Implementation at Community Level will comprise of the following groups: *Fadama* User Groups (FUGs), *Fadama* Development Facilitators (FDFs) and *Fadama* Community Associations (FCAs) Service Providers.

Rural Infrastructure

The development objective of *Fadama-III* Project is to increase the incomes of users of rural land and water resources on a sustainable basis. The project is anchored on the Community-Driven Development (CDD) approach. The approach creates sound conditions for sustainability of the small holder development strategy. The *Fadama* Project will help stimulate broad-based growth and expand employment opportunities in the non-oil economy by: (i) financing investments in productive community infrastructure to increase agricultural productivity and diversify livelihood sources; (ii) building the capacity of community organizations to increase the stock of social capital; (iii) strengthening the capabilities of participating state and local governments to deliver services to the rural poor; and (iv) promoting socially inclusive and environmentally-sustainable management of natural resources for non-oil growth [1].

Support to Agricultural Development Programmes (ADPs), Sponsored Research and On-Farm Demonstrations

This component has three sub-components, these are: Support to ADPs; Sponsored Research; and on- farm demonstration. Under the Support to ADPs sub-component the ADP aims at strengthening the Community Driven Development (CDD) approach in changing the extension service from the traditional top-down supply-push service by the government to a demand-pull private sector service. This will entail

the establishment of model extension programs customized for meeting the requirements of particular communities, based on contributory funds provided by the Federal, State and Local governments. The activities of such extension programs would be channeled through the ADPs. The Project provided support to the ADPs to carry out the following specific and limited functions:

- i. **Support to Advisory Service Providers:** The Project would provide specialized technical assistance, training, experience-sharing and knowledge-exchange opportunities to service providers, with emphasis on improving the quality, effectiveness, availability, affordability and timeliness of advisory services. The ADP will identify established public and/or private sector service providers, with a proven record. The training menu will include specific agricultural technologies, such as new varieties and cultivation methods, participatory methodologies and facilitation skills, marketing and enterprise management, improved cultural practices, soil fertility management, sound use of agro-chemicals, soil conservation practices, rational water management and sustainable pasture management as well as sustainable ecosystem management. The Project will finance the cost of training and mentoring activities, including contracting consultant services in areas in which the ADPs lack the necessary expertise, and production and provision of training materials.
- ii. **Quality Assurance of Advisory Services:** The project funded the incremental operating costs to allow the ADPs to certify service providers and provide technical quality control to ensure that the advisory services delivered to project beneficiaries meet established quality standards.
- iii. **Training of Extension Staff:** The project will fund focused training of extension staff. This activity will be contracted out by the NFRA to public/private research/extension centers and/or specialized institutions, under a PC. Limited external training will be provided in selected disciplines of high
- iv. **priority.** The training menu will include new methods of instruction and information dissemination for the ADPs, workshops/retreats and study visits designed to up-grade skills and acquire new ones to support demand-driven community investments.
- v. **Training of Facilitators:** In addition to the Training of Extension Staff, the project also, provided periodic support to the facilitators, including training, workshops on formulation of demand for advisory services, and participatory implementation and supervision of such activities, as well as to perform quality control functions in order to ensure that the subprojects emanating from the FCAs meet minimum technical standards.
- vi. **Development of an ICT Resource Clinic:** The project financed the setting up of a small ICT resource centre consisting of between 5 and 10 computers with full internet connectivity. The centre is to assist operations of ADPs in data coding, analysis and monitoring of farmers adoption of innovative project interventions. It will also allow access to new information and an update of techniques relevant for the training of FDF and the Service providers under the project [2]

Training

Trainings make up the road map for human and stakeholders capacity building. The training programme encapsulates mobilization, and capacity building through training and provision of technical assistance for achieving; socially-inclusive and participatory development of the Local Development Plan (LDP) as the basis for the active participation of the beneficiary rural communities in the planning and management of their development programs, including systematic training on various aspects of the sub-project cycle such as needs assessment, the collective design, identification and selection of investment activities as well as preparation, implementation and monitoring of the sub- projects; enhanced capacity of each group participating in project implementation to acquire the skills needed to effectively carry out their responsibilities; and the process and articulating the guidelines for preparing the Local Development Programme (LDP) and involving the *Fadama* Community Association.

The training exercise also aims at assisting the participating Local Governments to strengthen their role to enable them respond more to the needs of their communities as well as improve decision-making capabilities; and create capacity for investment planning, community mobilization as well as supervision and monitoring of community development projects. It is also the objective of the training component to provide technical assistance and resources for designing and operating communications education and information dissemination program for the project. In addition, the project would provide specialized technical assistance, training, experience-sharing and knowledge exchange opportunities to service providers, with emphasis on improving the quality, effectiveness, availability, affordability and timeliness of advisory services. The goal here is to provide professionalism and technical capacity in the advisory services business [2]. A training need arises when there is a shortfall in terms of a person's knowledge, understanding, skill and attitudes compared with what is required by the job, or by the demands of the assignment [1].

Asset Acquisition

Under the asset acquisition component, the project will scale-up the matching grant approach that was successfully piloted under *Fadama III*, to support *Fadama* user groups/ economic interest groups (FUGs/EIGs) and their apex *Fadama* Community Associations (FCAs). By this means the project seeks to provide seed money to empower smallholder and poor *Fadama* users (who will be assisted to form viable economic interest groups) to acquire capital assets which they would use to undertake a wide range of small-scale income-generating activities; and also mobilize Economic Interest Groups (EIGs) who were unorganized and widely dispersed across rural communities to form organized community groups [2]. Other objectives of the asset acquisition component include providing a mechanism through which individual beneficiaries are mobilized and formed into community groups to enable them gain practical financial experience as well as revenue from small income-generating activities thereby making them more attractive to be financed as a group by financial institution; contributing positively to the development of rural financial intermediation; and provide appropriate training to build a savings culture among FUGs.

Since a demand-driven planning approach was used during implementation, assets to be acquired are not specifically identified ex-ante. However, the scope of subprojects would include: improvements in existing farming systems for horticultural produce, grains, roots and tubers; rearing of small animals (birds, sheep, goats, pigs beekeeping); promotion of technologies and investments in the livestock sector, such as dual purpose cattle raising (diary and meat, hides and skins); aquaculture and smallholder fisheries production activities; diversification of production systems and micro-enterprise development in nontraditional crops (such as vanilla, macadamia, ginger gum Arabica, peppers, flowers, etc); and equipment and support for processing and value addition [1]. Others include establishment of seed and

plant nurseries; small farming equipment and tools; construction material for small-scale operations; small works and installations; small irrigation and drainage works and equipment, including water lifting and distribution equipment; plantations and nurseries; storage facilities for produce/ products; and soil and water conservation technologies that are proven to be profitable with short payback periods [1].

Fadama User's Equity Fund

This *Fadama Users' Equity Fund Operational Manual (FUEFOM)* cannot be used in isolation. It is intended for use in association with other essential *Fadama III* project documents. It is to enable the *Fadama User Groups (FUGs)* to establish a savings scheme in order to promote community level capitalization as well as to ensure sustainability of the investment activities with the matching grants and counterpart funds.

The *Fadama User's Equity Fund (FUEFs)* as second-generation funds would be invested by the FUGs at the community level according to priorities and mechanisms defined by them as the sole owners of the funds. The recovered amounts would thus remain as financial capital circulating in the community, or may take the form of physical capital depending on the investment decision made by the FUGs/private individual members of the FUGs. This capitalization fund would constitute the basis for the development of sustainable savings and loan schemes [2]. In addition, it would gradually evolve towards or link with existing financial intermediation systems (such as, savings and loan associations/institutions, credit unions and commercial banks) thereby contributing to financial deepening in the economy.

Initially, the savings can be in the form of a withholding, but as with the case for assets acquired with matching grants, the exact number of withholdings and other contributions into the FUEF cannot be determined *ex ante*. It is expected that a demand- driven planning approach shall be used during implementation and that the exact amounts to be contributed towards the FUEFs will be determined through a participatory process with the full involvement of members of the FUGs under the guidance of Facilitators. However, the FUEFs shall be owned and operated by the FUGs themselves. Meanwhile, funds for the FUEF shall be withheld from sales of produce/products acquired by FUGs from their economic activities benefiting from the matching grants:

(i) From the economically active FUGs:

The FUGs will set aside an agreed amount per productive cycle, with effect from the second productive cycle of the subproject life. This shall be at least 10 per cent of the asset replacement cost. This comes from member user fee. Also, the user-fee charge from non FUG members shall be part of the FUEF fund. The amount realised shall be deposited in a bank account opened with a formal financial institution opened for that purpose [1].

(ii) From the vulnerable FUGs:

The FUGs from their user fee both from members and non members will set aside an agreed amount per productive cycle with effect from the second productive cycle of the project life. The agreed amount shall be deposited into a bank account opened with a formal financial institution and shall be deposited into a bank account opened with a formal financial institution and shall constitute a revolving fund called the *Fadama Users' Equity Fund* [2].

A full-time rural financial specialist at the State *Fadama* Coordination Office level is responsible for supervising the implementation of the matching grant and coordinating the facilitators that are assisting FUGs to operate their FUEFs. The specialist uses NGOs, private consultants and other qualified service providers to ensure that the revolving funds are properly managed. The specialist in collaboration with these

groups, facilitates linkages between the FUGs/EIGs and their FUEFs and established financial institutions/intermediaries. In addition, he/she: provides capacity building and membership education to the groups; monitors and supervises all micro finance activities; work closely with facilitators to asses viable subprojects; provides technical guidelines on micro-finance including linkages, saving culture and accounts and auditing; sets up FUEF linkages at FCA level; and minimizes conflicts for use of common assets, and work with the local government councils [1].

a. *Fadama III* Additional Financing

Fadama I (Phase I of the National *Fadama* Development Project) was implemented during the 1993-1999 period and focused mainly on crop production, downstream activities such as processing, preservation and marketing were largely neglected. The design did not take into cognizance of need for spatial integration of the markets (creating of physical and market infrastructure). It also failed to take into consideration other *Fadama* resource users such as livestock producers, fishing folks, pastoralists and hunters, among others. The project did not also support post-harvest technology, which manifested in reduced crop prices and increased storage losses during the period [3-4]. The project development objective was to sustainably increase the incomes of the beneficiaries through empowering communities to take charge of their own development agenda through Community Drive Development (CDD) approach in project implementation in a socially inclusive manner [1]. *Fadama II* also provides special preferences to groups of youths, women (especially widows), physically challenged, the elderly and people with HIV/AIDs. *Fadama III* project was conceived by the World Bank consequent upon the achievement and impact of *Fadama I* and *II* on the livelihood of rural dwellers; the programme becomes loan effective from July 30, 2008 and closed down on December 30, 2013. The programme was a follow-up to the *Fadama II* project which takes the CDD approach, which places 45 beneficiaries in driver's seat. Local community members under the umbrella of *Fadama* Community Associations [FCAs and *Fadama* Users Groups (FUGs)], oversee the design and implementation of the project and are empowered through skills and capacity building to improve their livelihoods by increasing income generating activities. According to International Development Agency, the project was designed to focus on increasing the incomes of rural poor; the project will help reduce rural poverty, increase food security and contribute to the achievement of a key Millenium Development Goal. Consequently, because of the tremendous achievements recorded by the *Fadama III* Interventions, Additional Financing of the *Fadama III* was approved on 29th May, 2016 in Benue State with aims to scale up the impacts and development of effectiveness of a well-performing project by aligning it more closely with the new Agricultural Transformation Agenda that was adopted by the government of Nigeria in 2011. It aimed to support cluster of farmers in selected States with comparative advantage and high potential to increase production and productivity of cassava, rice and sorghum and horticulture value chains and link them to better organized markets, within the selected states. Over the years, many studies were conducted on the impact of *Fadama I*, *II* and *III* on its impact on the benefiting communities.

b. *Fadama III* Peer Review

At the end of the *Fadama III* Additional Financing programme (2017 -2020), the *Fadama III* Peer Review programme was embarked upon and its implementation is on-oing. The aim is to assess the achievement of all the Prgramme in the areas where it has been implemented with the aim of ensuring that the programme achieve its goal. In areas where the programme fails short in its implementation process, some funds are provided to help in areas of assets acquisition and input support.

Bottom- Top Approach used in Third *Fadama* Development Programme

The development objective of *Fadama*-III Project was to increase the incomes of users of rural land and water resources on a sustainable basis. The project was anchored on the Community-Driven Development approach which creates sound conditions for sustainability of the small holder development strategy. The third FDP incorporated the community-driven development (CDD) approach in which the beneficiaries were assisted to organize into economically sustainable *Fadama* Resource User Groups, which participated in the design of project activities, their implementation and monitoring. Government will play the catalytic roles of providing a conducive policy and institutional environment through investments in improving relevant physical infrastructure as well as make provision for goods of a public nature. Government would also put in place an appropriate regulatory system to ensure that project clients obtain regular supplies of the right quality of inputs and technical advice and up-to-date market information; and to ensure the sustainable and equitable exploitation of *Fadama* resources by all resource users [5].

Fadama Programme and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) also known as the Global Goals, were adopted by the United Nations in 2015 as a Universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure that by 2030 all people enjoy peace and prosperity. The 17 SDGs are integrated—they recognize that action in one area will affect outcomes in others, and that development must balance social, economic and environmental sustainability. The 17-point targets of the SDGs are: no poverty, zero hunger, good health and well-being, quality education, gender equality, clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, and industry, innovation and infrastructure. Others are reduced inequalities, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action, life below water, life on land, peace, justice and strong institutions, and partnerships for the goals [6].

The focus of *Fadama* programme on improving agricultural productivity, incomes and poverty reduction is therefore, in line with the first and second goals of the SDGs to eradicate poverty and hunger. This is because increased agricultural productivity brings about food security and consequently reduces extreme hunger among the citizenry.

Criticisms and Challenges of the Implementation of Third *Fadama* Programme in Nigeria

Dimelu et al. [7] observes that although one of the key features of the project is to empower the communities to collectively decide on how resources are allocated and managed for their livelihood activities and to participate in the design and execution of their sub-projects, and unlike the first and second phases of the Project, *Fadama III* introduced new components (public ADP and adaptive research support) and several sub-components (sustainable land management, *Fadama* User Equity Fund etc.); moreover, *Fadama III* also has a stronger emphasis on production through its ADP support and research, as well as demand-driven advisory services and input support. The project set a goal of increasing agricultural productivity by 60 percent, a goal that was not set explicitly under *Fadama II* that the approach of the Project, though community driven seems not to have accommodated the priority needs of the farmers; practically, it undermines the key element of participatory and demand driven approach because the operations at the local level are not farmer-driven. *Fadama* beneficiaries did not benefit from the Agricultural Development Program (ADP) support and adaptive research component and their advisory service was not demand responsive as it was designed to be due to poor payment of allowance. Bature et al. [8] also

suggested that *Fadama III* need to improve on the following areas; better targeting of the poor and vulnerable, funding sustainable methods of promoting development of rural financial users to manage the productive assets efficiently. They also opined that these issues are interrelated and therefore need to be considered simultaneously.

Achiv *et al.* [9] study on evaluation of Third National *Fadama* Development Programme (*Fadama III*) on poverty reduction in rural communities of Buruku local government area of Benue State identified corrupt practices such as embezzlements and mismanagement of funds by both rural and state management officials of *Fadama III* programme, untimely and inadequate supply of inputs and difficulties of member communities to pay counterpart funds as major constraints to effective implementation of *Fadama III* programme in the study area. Girei *et al.* [5] while assessing the problems associated to *Fadama* crop farming in Adamawa State concluded that inadequate and high cost of fertilizer was reported to be very severe and serious problem affecting the crop farmers of *Fadama*. Other challenges were high cost of agrochemicals (which was not a severe problem), non-availability of improved seeds (also a non-severe problem), clashes with pastoralist, high cost of paid labour, high cost of water pumps and inadequate supply of water during some months. Also, [10] who studied on Gender-Based Evaluation of World Bank Assisted *Fadama III* Farm Inputs Distribution Programme among User Groups in Benue State, Nigeria found that the major constraints that affected *Fadama III* farm input utilization in the study area were land tenure, inadequate fund, inadequate labour supply, conflict among the user group members and inadequate storage facilities. *Fadama III* is constrained by these problems, which is why it could not make much impact in the rural areas. The author [11] in his study on assessment of the implementation of World Bank Assisted *Fadama III* Project in Benue State identified delay in payment of counterpart fund by User Groups, delay in payment of counter fund by the government, delay in the release of IMF funds to beneficiaries, poor facilitation by project facilitators, inadequate training of beneficiaries, inadequate training facilities, inadequate training of Desk Officers and poor advisory and input support as the challenges of *Fadama III* in Nigeria. Also, the majority of farmers were illiterate and lacked basic knowledge of water requirement, irrigation scheduling, and skills in maintaining and operating the pumps. This affects the yield of crops as the crops are either over - or under -irrigated, leading to wastage of the little available water. Erosion is a serious problem during the rainy season and coupled with continuous use of land, low fertility results.

Conclusion

The main conclusion from the study is that *Fadama III* programme that help reduce poverty in Benue State through capacity building, communications and information support as well as rural infrastructure. In addition, results showed that saving culture among *Fadama* User Groups (FUGs), is needed in order to promote community level capitalization as well as to ensure sustainability of the investment activities with the matching grants and counterpart funds. Furthermore, results also identified some challenges of the *Fadama III* programme and due to these findings, it was therefore recommended that administrators of the

programme give proper attention to issues relating to timely disbursement of the programme grant as this is a core militating factor identified in the implementation of the programme in Benue State.

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